

Characterisation of Some Solid Products Obtained by Carrying Out the Replacement Reactions on the Hydrated Sulphates of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) Using Two Different Heterocyclic Ligands viz., Antifuran-2-carboxaldoxime and 2-pyrrolidone

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Treatment of hydrated sulphates of copper(II), nickel(II) or cobalt(II) with the two ligands, antifuran-2-carboxaldoxime (FDH) and 2-pyrrolidone (pyrr) separately, forms compounds: $[\text{Cu}(\text{FDH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{SO}_4$, $[\text{Ni}$ or $\text{Co}(\text{FDH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{SO}_4$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{pyrr})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{SO}_4$ and $[\text{Ni}$ or $\text{Co}(\text{pyrr})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{SO}_4$. The analytical, molar conductance, magnetic and spectroscopic data suggest square planar structure for copper(II) complexes and octahedral structure for nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes.

It was shown in our earlier publications that a number of solid complexes were obtained by replacing some of the coordinated water molecules from Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) hydrated sulphates by using such neutral ligands as aromatic and heterocyclic amines, thiourea, heterocyclic Schiffs bases and oximes¹⁻⁵. In most of the cases only two water molecules could be replaced easily while the third one could be replaced only if some stronger ligands like chelating di or triamines were used¹⁻³. The present paper deals with a similar study using antifuran-2-carboxaldoxime and 2-pyrrolidone as ligands.

Experimental

A known weight of hydrated copper(II), nickel(II) or cobalt(II) sulphate was suspended in methanol and equimolar amount of the ligand, dissolved in methanol, was added dropwise while the mixture was kept under reflux continuously*. After the addition of the ligand was completed, the reaction mixture was further refluxed for 5 hr and the complex was crystallized out from the solution by repeated treatment with petroleum spirit.

Discussion

On the basis of elemental analysis and molar conductance values (Table 1), the molecular formulae assigned to the complexes are $[\text{Cu}(\text{FDH})$ or $(\text{pyrr})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{SO}_4$ and $[\text{Ni}$ or $\text{Co}(\text{FDH})$ or $(\text{pyrr})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{SO}_4$ which show that only two coordinated water molecules have been replaced from the parent hydrated metal(II) sulphate by one

ligand molecule. In the ir spectra of all these complexes a sharp νOH band characteristic of coordinated water appears at $\sim 3420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ while the bands due to ν_3 and ν_4 modes of uncoordinated sulphate ions appear at 1110 and 650 cm^{-1} , respectively.

The thermogravimetric measurements on the complexes in the temperature range of 20 to 800° show no weight loss around 100° indicating the absence of lattice water. The loss in weight between 240 and 400° corresponds to the loss of two molecules of water and one molecule of the ligand. The metal(II) sulphate, thus formed remains stable between 400 and 500° and decomposes to the metal oxide upto 600° which remains stable till 800° .

In the spectrum of the free ligand antifuran-2-carboxaldoxime (I), the bands corresponding to the

intramolecularly bonded $-\text{OH}$ group appear at 3160 and 3040 cm^{-1} , while these merge together in the complexes and only one sharp band appears at 3360 cm^{-1} . This shows the cleavage of hydrogen bonding of oxime oxygen⁶⁻⁷, which is also supported by the raising of $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ of the free ligand from 1640 to 1660 cm^{-1} in the complexes^{8,9}. Furthermore, the appearance of two sharp bands at 670 ($\nu\text{M}-\text{O}_{\text{oxime}}$) and 510 cm^{-1} ($\nu\text{M}-\text{O}_{\text{furan}}$) suggests the coordination of the ligand through furan ring and oxime oxygens¹⁰⁻¹².

* Even if the ligands are added in excess only one equivalent of the same (corresponding to the replacement of two water molecules) is consumed in the reaction. The other equivalents remain unreacted even after continued refluxing.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND TGA DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complexes	%M	%C	%H	%N	%SO ₄	% of H ₂ O and ligand lost at 280-400°	μ_{eff} in B.M.	λ in mhos in nitro benzene
1. [Cu(FDH)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	20.95 (20.72)*	20.15 (19.57)	3.60 (2.95)	4.70 (4.56)	31.99 (31.31)	48.09 (47.96)	1.884	24.8
2. [Ni(FDH)(H ₂ O) ₄]SO ₄	14.98 (15.70)	15.87 (16.06)	3.10 (3.50)	3.27 (3.74)	24.81 (24.69)	53.98 (54.20)	3.208	26.2
3. [Co(FDH)(H ₂ O) ₄]SO ₄	16.71 (17.42)	16.97 (17.76)	3.43 (3.87)	4.02 (4.14)	27.48 (28.41)	54.10 (54.18)	4.950	25.0
4. [Cu(H ₂ O) ₂ (pyrr)]SO ₄	22.10 (22.67)	16.92 (17.11)	3.56 (3.92)	4.81 (4.92)	33.62 (34.22)	42.99 (43.13)	1.882	22.6
5. [Ni(H ₂ O) ₄ (pyrr)]SO ₄	17.41 (18.82)	14.93 (15.40)	5.05 (4.84)	4.30 (4.49)	29.44 (30.79)	50.80 (50.36)	3.082	21.9
6. [Co(H ₂ O) ₄ (pyrr)]SO ₄	17.20 (18.87)	16.01 (15.39)	4.94 (4.84)	4.50 (4.40)	29.81 (30.77)	50.07 (50.34)	4.608	28.2

* The figures in parenthesis indicate Calcd. values.

In free 2-pyrrolidone, the ν_{NH} and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ stretching frequencies are observed at 3300 and 1700 cm^{-1} , both of which undergo considerable negative shift in complexes and occur at 3250 cm^{-1} and 1665 cm^{-1} respectively showing coordination through these sites.

The copper(II) complexes are, thus, four coordinate with μ_{eff} values in the range 1.82-1.88 B.M. The appearance of a band at $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ associated with a shoulder at $\sim 1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is indicative of a square planar stereochemistry.

The μ_{eff} values of both the nickel(II) complexes are around 3.20 B.M. suggesting an octahedral stereochemistry. In the electronic spectra, three bands at 25,310, 13,980 and 9,660 cm^{-1} , assigned to $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(\text{P}) (\nu_2)$, $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(\text{F}) (\nu_2)$ and $3A_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow 3T_{2g}(\text{F}) (\nu_1)$ transitions, along with the D_q and B values of 966 cm^{-1} and 850 cm^{-1} confirm an octahedral structure¹⁸⁻²¹.

The room temperature μ_{eff} values of the two cobalt(II) complexes may either indicate a tetrahedral or octahedral structure but the values at two lower temperatures (257°K, 143°K) show a considerable decrease as shown below, suggesting the latter geometry since the μ_{eff} values for the tetrahedral complexes should be independent of temperature¹⁷.

	μ_{eff} at 303°K	μ_{eff} at 257°K	μ_{eff} at 143°K
Complex no. 3	4.95 B.M.	4.36 B.M.	3.92 B.M.
Complex no. 6	4.61 B.M.	4.08 B.M.	3.65 B.M.

This assignment of octahedral structure is further confirmed by the presence of a sharp band at 20,000 cm^{-1} [$4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(\text{P})$] and another weak and broad one at 9,900 cm^{-1} [$4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow 4T_{2g}(\text{F})$]

and the derived D_q and B values of 844 and 879 cm^{-1} ¹⁸⁻²¹.

References

- P. R. SHUKLA and N. VERMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 810.
- P. R. SHUKLA and N. VERMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, **19A**, 272.
- P. R. SHUKLA and R. TAKROO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).
- P. R. SHUKLA and A. M. JAISWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).
- P. R. SHUKLA and V. K. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).
- A. R. KATRITZKY, "Physical Methods in Heterocyclic Chemistry", 1963, **11**, 199.
- K. TAKANO, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1961, **82**, 373.
- K. BURGER, F. RUFF, I. RUFF and I. EGGED, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1965, **46**.
- K. BURGER, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1955, **27**, 2361.
- J. R. NIEDZIELSKI and C. ZAIDER, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1965, **213**, 1618.
- H. K. HALL and R. ZBINDEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 6428.
- M. P. COAKLEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 1937.
- A. CHAKRAVARTY and T. S. KHANNA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 1691.
- L. E. ORGAS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1955, **23**, 6.
- W. C. FRENELINS and W. MANEN, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1961, **38**, 192.
- J. MICHAEL and R. A. WALTON, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 71.
- B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1966, p. 287.
- D. R. LORENZ, T. M. BARBARA and J. R. WASSER, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.*, 1976, **12**, 65.
- E. W. AIZISCOUGH, A. M. BRODIE and K. C. PALMER, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 1976, 2375.
- H. YOKOI and T. ISOBE, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1969, **42**, 2187.
- B. P. KENNEDY and A. B. P. LEVER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1973, **95**, 6907.